

FUZZY LOGIC-BASED LONG SHORT-TERM MEMORY NEURAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURES FOR FINANCIAL TIME SERIES FORECASTING

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Abstract. *Forecasting financial time series remains a challenging task due to high volatility, nonlinear relationships, and the presence of noise in market data. Traditional statistical approaches often struggle to capture these complex patterns, while deep learning methods have demonstrated promising results in modelling sequential dependencies. In this study, we investigate a neural network architecture that combines Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks with principles of fuzzy logic for financial time series forecasting. The proposed approach introduces fuzzy logic both at the data preprocessing stage and within the neural network itself. During preprocessing, fuzzification of input data is used to represent financial observations as fuzzy sets, allowing the model to better handle uncertainty and reduce sensitivity to noise. In addition, fuzzy concepts are incorporated into the network through modified activation functions, which can be interpreted as membership functions of fuzzy sets. This design enables the model to perform operations analogous to fuzzy inference while learning temporal dependencies in the data. Experimental results on financial datasets demonstrate that the proposed fuzzy-enhanced LSTM architecture improves forecasting accuracy compared with a standard LSTM model. The findings suggest that integrating fuzzy logic with recurrent neural networks provides a promising direction for improving financial time series prediction.*

Keywords: *financial time series forecasting, Long Short-Term Memory, Fuzzy logic, Activation functions, Recurrent neural networks.*

Introduction

Financial time series forecasting represents a fundamental problem in economics and finance. Accurate predictions of financial dynamics are essential for a wide range of applications, including algorithmic trading, portfolio management, risk assessment, and macroeconomic analysis. Despite its practical importance, forecasting financial time series remains a challenging task. This difficulty arises from several intrinsic characteristics of financial data, such as non-stationarity, nonlinear relationships between variables, and the presence of significant noise in market observations (Shiryayev, 2016).

Traditional statistical approaches, including models such as ARIMA and GARCH, have been widely used to analyse and predict financial time series. While these models provide a well-established theoretical framework, their ability to capture complex nonlinear structures and rapidly changing market dynamics is often limited (Andersen et al., 2009). In recent years, deep learning techniques have gained substantial attention in the field of financial forecasting. In particular, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and their more advanced variants, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, have demonstrated strong performance in modelling sequential data and learning long-term temporal dependencies (Sezer et al., 2020). These architectures are

especially well suited for time series analysis due to their capacity to retain information from previous observations.

Nevertheless, conventional LSTM models also exhibit several limitations. In particular, they tend to be sensitive to noise in financial datasets and typically rely on fixed activation functions, which restricts their ability to adapt to the specific characteristics of different financial time series. In this study, we propose the application of fuzzy logic to enhance financial time series forecasting. Fuzzy logic enables flexible data processing by accounting for uncertainty and variability inherent in financial markets. This approach can be integrated into neural network models at several stages.

First, fuzzy logic can be applied during the preprocessing stage through the fuzzification of input data. In this process, numerical observations are transformed into fuzzy sets, which helps to smooth noisy fluctuations and represent uncertainty more effectively. Several approaches to modelling fuzzy time series have been proposed in the literature, including representations based on linguistic variables, fuzziness distributed over time, and fuzziness distributed across the value domain (Afanasyeva et al., 2014). In addition, Hesitant Fuzzy Sets (HFS) have been used for forecasting tasks, such as predicting university admission scores in Alabama and modelling stock prices of Indian companies (Bisht & Kumar, 2016).

Another way to incorporate fuzzy logic into neural networks is through the use of fuzzy activation functions. By modifying the slope and shift parameters of activation functions, it becomes possible to adapt the behaviour of the network to the characteristics of a specific time series. In our previous work, we demonstrated that activation functions such as cloglog and loglog, which can be interpreted as transformations of the sigmoid function, may improve forecasting performance (Kumskov et al., 2025). Recent studies have also explored parametric and fuzzy activation functions as a means of improving the performance of deep neural networks (Bingham & Miikkulainen, 2022; Beke & Kumbasar, 2019).

The main objective of this study is to investigate recurrent neural network architectures with memory that incorporate principles of fuzzy logic in order to improve the accuracy of financial time series forecasting. The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews related research on financial time series forecasting, including traditional statistical approaches, neural network models, and hybrid fuzzy–neural systems. Section 3 presents the theoretical background relevant to this study, including the principles of fuzzy logic and the main characteristics of financial time series. Section 4 formulates the problem statement. Section 5 describes the architecture and operation of LSTM networks. Section 6 presents the proposed model together with the results of computational experiments and their analysis. Finally, the Conclusion summarises the main findings and outlines potential directions for future research.

Related work

Financial time series forecasting has been widely investigated using a variety of approaches, including statistical methods, machine learning techniques, and hybrid intelligent models (Praveen et al., 2025). Traditional statistical models, such as ARIMA and GARCH, have long been applied to analyse financial data and model temporal dependencies. These methods are effective in capturing linear relationships in time series; however, they often struggle to adequately represent the nonlinear and highly volatile nature of financial markets (Andersen et al., 2009; Shiryaev, 2016). Consequently, more flexible and adaptive forecasting models have attracted increasing attention in recent years.

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) have become one of the most widely used tools for financial time series prediction (Sezer et al., 2020). Architectures such as feedforward neural networks (FFNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) have demonstrated promising results in modelling complex temporal patterns (Du et al., 2021). In particular, advanced recurrent architectures including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) networks are capable of learning long-term dependencies in sequential data (Hewamalage et al., 2021). Nevertheless, the performance of neural network models strongly depends on appropriate parameter tuning, feature representation, and preprocessing techniques. Furthermore, conventional neural networks often remain sensitive to noise and sudden fluctuations in financial data.

To address uncertainty and improve the interpretability of forecasting models, fuzzy logic has been incorporated into time series analysis. Fuzzy-based approaches allow the modelling of vague and imprecise information that commonly occurs in financial datasets (Orang et al., 2023). Recent studies have proposed hybrid models that combine fuzzy clustering with optimisation techniques, such as Grey Wolf Optimisation (GWO) and the Sine–Cosine Algorithm (SCA), to optimise Markov weights and improve the modelling of fuzzy relationships within time series (Yang et al., 2017).

The combination of fuzzy logic and neural networks has led to the development of neuro–fuzzy systems, which integrate the interpretability of fuzzy inference with the learning capabilities of neural networks (Kan et al., 2024). One of the earliest and most well-known frameworks of this type is the Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) (Wei, 2016).

More recent research has also focused on improving neural network adaptability through the use of fuzzy and parametric activation functions (Bingham & Miikkulainen, 2022; Beke & Kumbasar, 2019). In our previous work, we demonstrated that activation functions derived from transformations of the sigmoid function, such as the cloglog and loglog functions, can improve the predictive performance of LSTM-based forecasting models (Kumskov et al., 2025). Building upon these findings, the model proposed in the present study integrates fuzzy logic both at the data preprocessing stage and within the neural network architecture, combining input fuzzification with adaptive fuzzy activation mechanisms in the LSTM framework.

Basic Definitions and Notation

Financial Time Series

Definition 1. Time series. A time series X is defined as a sequence of chronologically ordered real-valued vectors:

$$X = (x(t_1), x(t_2), \dots, x(t_n)), x(t_i) \in \mathbb{R}^m$$

The number n is denoted as $|X|$ and represents the length of the series. A constant time step is referred to as a tick: $\Delta t = t_i - t_{i-1}$

Definition 2. Financial time series. Financial time series exhibit several distinctive characteristics. In particular, the formation of financial indices and asset prices is typically nonlinear and demonstrates temporal dependence, meaning that many financial variables retain information about past observations (Shiryaev, 2016).

Financial Time Series Forecasting Tasks

Financial time series forecasting tasks can generally be divided into two main categories depending on the expected output of the model (Sezer et al., 2020). Price forecasting refers to predicting the numerical value of an asset at a future point in time or over a specified forecasting

horizon. Trend forecasting focuses on predicting the direction of price movement rather than the exact value. This task can be formulated as a classification problem:

- Two-class problem – predicting whether the trend will be upward or downward.
- Three-class problem – predicting whether the trend will be upward, downward, or sideways.

The input data used for forecasting financial time series may originate from several sources:

- Historical prices. Past price observations and trading data collected over previous time periods.
- Fundamental analysis. Analytical methods used to estimate the intrinsic or fair value of an asset and to assess potential changes in market demand.
- Technical analysis. The study of price charts and historical trading patterns in order to identify signals that may indicate future price movements.
- Textual information. Information extracted from financial news, social media posts, and online discussions. Sentiment analysis techniques are often used to evaluate market opinions and predict investor behaviour.

Fuzzy Logic

Definition 3. Fuzzy set. A fuzzy set is defined as a pair (U, m) , where U denotes the universe of discourse and $m: U \rightarrow [0,1]$ is the membership function. For each $x \in U$ the value $m(x)$ represents the degree of membership of the element x in the fuzzy set (U, m)

In the context of this study, x corresponds to an observed value of a financial time series (for example, the price of an asset at time t_i), while U denotes the range of possible price values. For a finite universe $U = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, a fuzzy set (U, m) can be represented as

$$\{m(x_1)/x_1, \dots, m(x_n)/x_n\}$$

Let $x \in U$. Then the membership function satisfies

$$m(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \text{ does not belong to the fuzzy set} \\ 1, & x \text{ fully belongs to the fuzzy set} \\ 0 < m(x) < 1, & x \text{ partially belongs to the fuzzy set} \end{cases}$$

Operations on Fuzzy Sets. The basic operations on fuzzy sets are defined as follows. The intersection of two fuzzy sets (fuzzy “AND”) is given by $m_{A \cap B}(x) = \min(m_A(x), m_B(x))$. The union of two fuzzy sets (fuzzy “OR”) is defined as $m_A(x) = \max(m_A(x), m_B(x))$

Variables. To formally describe fuzzy sets, the notions of fuzzy variables and linguistic variables are introduced. **Definition 4.** Fuzzy variable. A fuzzy variable is defined by the triplet (N, U, A) , where: N is the name of the variable, U is the universe of discourse, A is a fuzzy set defined on U . The values of a linguistic variable can themselves be fuzzy variables. Therefore, a linguistic variable represents a higher-level abstraction. Each linguistic variable consists of the following components: a name; a set of values, also referred to as the base term set T ; the universe of discourse U ; a syntactic rule G for generating new linguistic terms using natural or formal language constructs; a semantic rule P that assigns to each value of the linguistic variable a corresponding fuzzy subset of U

Membership Functions. Membership functions are used to describe the degree to which an element belongs to a fuzzy set. A variety of functional forms can be used to represent membership functions. Among them, the most commonly applied are triangular, trapezoidal, and Gaussian membership functions (see Table 1). In addition to these classical forms, certain

activation functions whose values lie within the interval $[0, 1]$ can also be interpreted as membership functions. Examples include S-shaped functions such as **sigmoid**, **cloglog**, and **loglog**, as well as their modified variants with shifted centres or adjusted slopes.

Table 1. Types of membership functions.

Type	Parameters	Formula
Triangular	(a, b, c)	$m(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{b-x}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b, \\ 1 - \frac{x-b}{c-b}, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$
Trapezoidal	(a, b, c, d)	$m(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{b-x}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b, \\ 1, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 1 - \frac{x-c}{d-c}, & c \leq x \leq d \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$
Gaussian	(c, σ)	$m(x) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x-c}{\sigma}\right)^2\right)$
Sigmoid	(α, β)	$m(x) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\alpha(x - \beta))}$
Cloglog	(α, β)	$m(x) = 1 - \exp(-\exp(\alpha(x - \beta)))$
Loglog	(α, β)	$m(x) = \exp(-\exp(-\alpha(x - \beta)))$

Figure 1 illustrates an example of a linguistic variable called “Stock price”. The corresponding fuzzy variables are “low”, “moderate”, and “high”. The universe of discourse is defined within a specific range of possible price values.

Figure 1. Example of the linguistic variable “Stock price”. The fuzzy variables are low, moderate, and high. The universe of discourse is defined as $U=[100,200]$. The membership degree of the value 160 is 0 for the set low, 0.75 for the set moderate, and 0.40 for the set high.

Fuzzy Inference. Fuzzy inference is based on a *rule base* that contains fuzzy rules together with membership functions corresponding to linguistic terms. The inference process typically consists of four stages: fuzzification, fuzzy inference, composition, and defuzzification (see Fig. 2). Different fuzzy inference algorithms mainly differ in the structure of the rule base, the logical operations applied, and the defuzzification method used (Rutkovskaya et al., 2006).

Figure 2. Fuzzy inference mechanism. Crisp input data X are first fuzzified, producing fuzzy input values \tilde{X} . Fuzzy inference is then performed using a predefined rule base. The resulting fuzzy output \tilde{Y} . Is subsequently defuzzified to obtain the final crisp output Y .

Problem Statement

Let us consider a one-dimensional financial time series of asset prices observed at discrete time moments. The time series can be represented as a sequence of values where the observations are recorded at a constant time interval (tick) $\Delta t \in \{\text{minute, hour, day}\}$

$$X = (x(t_1), x(t_2), \dots, x(t_n)), \quad x(t_i) \in \mathbb{R}$$

The forecasting task consists in predicting future values of the time series k ticks ahead, which can be written as $Y = (y(t_{n+1}), y(t_{n+2}), \dots, y(t_{n+k}))$. The general structure of the proposed forecasting model follows the scheme of fuzzy inference (see Fig. 3). In the proposed approach, fuzzy inference is implemented using a neural network with modified activation functions. In this framework, activation functions are interpreted as membership functions, allowing the network to operate on fuzzy representations of the input data.

Figure 3. General scheme of the proposed model. Crisp input data X are first fuzzified, producing fuzzy input values \tilde{X} . Fuzzy inference is then performed using a predefined rule base. The resulting fuzzy output \tilde{Y} . Is subsequently defuzzified to obtain the final crisp output Y .

Fuzzification

There are several approaches to introducing fuzziness into financial time series data.

Gaussian Fuzzification. One possible approach is to associate each observation of the time series with a fuzzy set defined by a Gaussian membership function (see Fig. 4). In this representation, the original time series values are treated as the centres of Gaussian membership functions. For each time moment t_i , the observed value x_i is associated with a fuzzy set whose membership function is defined as follows:

$$m_i(x) = \exp\left(-\frac{(x - x_i)^2}{2\sigma_{i-1}^2}\right)$$

The parameter σ_{i-1} represents the local volatility, which is estimated over the previous observations within the window $[t_{i-1}, t_{i-1}]$. Using the shifted volatility σ_{i-1} ensures causal fuzzification, meaning that the uncertainty at time t_i depends only on information available from previous observations.

Figure 4. Example of Gaussian fuzzification of a time series. The black dots represent the observed values x_i , while the Gaussian curves correspond to fuzzy sets associated with each time point t_i

Additionally, an auxiliary feature is introduced:

$$m_i(x_{i-1}) = \exp\left(-\frac{(x_{i-1} - x_i)^2}{2\sigma_{i-1}^2}\right)$$

This value represents the degree of membership of the previous observation x_{i-1} to the fuzzy set centred at the current value x_i . As a result, the fuzzy representation of the time series contains two input channels: the normalised price value (the centre of the Gaussian set) and the membership degree $m_i(x_{i-1})$.

Probabilistic Fuzzy Sets. Another approach to fuzzification is based on probabilistic fuzzy sets (Gupta & Kumar, 2018). The procedure consists of the following steps:

1. Define the universe of discourse $U = [X_{min} - \sigma, X_{max} + \sigma]$ where X_{min} and X_{max} denote the minimum and maximum values of the time series within the observation window, and σ represents the variance.
2. Partition the universe U into n equal intervals e_i
3. Construct fuzzy sets F_i over these intervals using triangular membership functions (see Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Construction of probabilistic fuzzy sets. The universe of discourse U is divided into intervals e_i , and fuzzy sets F_i are defined over these intervals using triangular membership functions.

Linguistic Variables. An alternative approach is to reformulate the forecasting task as a classification problem. In this case, the model predicts categories such as the price level, trend direction, or even the sentiment of market participants. For this formulation, fuzzy sets are defined for the corresponding linguistic variables using triangular or trapezoidal membership functions. An example of such a representation is shown in Fig. 1.

Fuzziness and Activation Functions

Let ϕ_θ denote an activation function parameterised by a set of parameters θ that determine its shape, such as the centre and slope of the function. The objective is to determine the optimal parameters θ^* of the activation function that minimise the forecasting error of the financial time series.

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_\theta \mathcal{L}(X, y, \theta)$$

Where $\mathcal{L}(X, y, \theta)$ denotes the loss function measuring the discrepancy between the predicted and observed values of the time series. The parameters θ include both the internal parameters of the neural network and the parameters governing the shape of the activation functions. As discussed earlier, S-shaped activation functions such as the sigmoid function and its variants with shifted centres or modified slopes can be interpreted as membership functions of fuzzy sets. Since a neural network consists of layers of neurons performing transformations through activation functions, it can be viewed as a composition of fuzzy transformations. In this interpretation, the network operates on fuzzy representations of the input data, and therefore can be regarded as a computational model of fuzzy inference.

Defuzzification.

The fuzzy outputs produced by the neural network must be converted into crisp numerical forecasts. This process is known as defuzzification.

Gaussian-Based Defuzzification. In the Gaussian fuzzification framework, the model produces a predicted value \hat{x}_{i+1} at time t_{i+1} . The final crisp forecast is obtained by combining this predicted value with the previous centre of fuzzy set x_i using the membership degree m_i .

$$y_{i+1} = \hat{m}_{i+1} x_i + (1 - \hat{m}_{i+1})\hat{x}_{i+1}$$

This adaptive defuzzification mechanism acts as a smoothing operator, increasing the stability of the resulting forecast, particularly for highly volatile financial time series.

Probabilistic Fuzzy Sets. In the case of probabilistic fuzzy sets, triangular membership functions are defined over the partitioned universe of discourse. Given the predicted degrees of membership for each fuzzy set, a unique crisp forecast can be obtained by aggregating these membership values and computing the corresponding numerical estimate.

Linguistic Variables. When the forecasting task is formulated in terms of linguistic variables (for example, price levels such as low, moderate, or high), defuzzification is performed in an analogous manner by converting the predicted fuzzy output into a single crisp value.

Long Short-Term Memory architecture

A recurrent neural network (RNN) consists of repeating computational modules connected in a sequential chain. In this work, we employ the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architecture, which represents a specialised type of RNN designed to capture long-term dependencies in sequential data. The unrolled structure of the LSTM network used in the proposed model is illustrated in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Unrolled structure of the LSTM network used in the proposed model. The sequence of recurrent cells performs the fuzzy inference stage, where fuzzified financial time series data are sequentially processed by LSTM units with parametric activation functions before the defuzzification step.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks extend classical recurrent neural networks by introducing memory cells and gating mechanisms that regulate the flow of information through the network. Unlike standard RNN units, an LSTM module contains four interacting components, which allow the model to selectively retain or discard information (see Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Architecture of an LSTM cell. Each line represents the transfer of a vector from the output of one node to the input of another. Merging lines indicate concatenation, while

branching arrows denote data duplication across multiple components of the network. The notation is as follows: c_t – cell state, x_t – input vector, h_t – output (hidden state), \times – elementwise multiplication, $+$ – vector addition, σ – sigmoid layer, and \tanh – hyperbolic tangent layer.

This architecture enables efficient modelling of long-term dependencies in sequential data, allowing the network to recognise patterns over extended time intervals, identify events separated by long time gaps, and extract temporal relationships embedded in the data (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997).

At each time step t , the LSTM module receives the input vector x_t together with the previous hidden state h_{t-1} . The behaviour of a standard LSTM cell can be described by the following system of equations, where W denote weight matrices and b denote bias vectors.

Forget Gate. $f_t = \sigma_f(W_f [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f)$ The forget gate determines which information from the previous cell state should be retained.

Input Gate $i_t = \sigma_i(W_i [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i)$ The input gate controls how much new information should be written into the cell state.

Candidate Cell State. $\tilde{c}_t = \tanh(W_c [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c)$. This step generates candidate values that may update the internal memory of the LSTM cell.

Cell State Update. $c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tilde{c}_t$ The cell state combines the retained information from the previous step with the new candidate values.

Output Gate $o_t = \sigma_o(W_o [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o)$ The output gate determines which part of the cell state should be exposed to the next layer.

Hidden State $h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(c_t)$ The hidden state represents the output of the LSTM unit at time step t .

In the proposed approach, the activation functions within the LSTM architecture are parameterised and interpreted as adaptive membership functions, allowing the network to perform fuzzy inference directly within its recurrent structure.

Computational Experiment

Description of the Computational Experiment

Data Collection The data used in the computational experiments were obtained from the Yahoo Finance platform using the yfinance Python library (Aroussi, 2025). For the analysis and forecasting tasks, historical quotations of BTC-USD (Bitcoin to US dollar) were used with three different temporal resolutions: 1 minute, 1 hour, and 1 day.

The experimental periods were defined as follows:

- 1-minute interval: the most recent week of available data;
- 1-hour interval: the previous 730 days;
- 1-day interval: the entire available historical record.

The collected data were preprocessed using normalisation followed by the proposed fuzzification procedure. After preprocessing, the dataset was divided chronologically into training (75 %) and testing (25%) subsets. This temporal split ensures realistic forecasting conditions and prevents data leakage between past and future observations. The original time series values ranged approximately from 20,000 USD to 120,000 USD, which should be taken into account when interpreting the forecasting performance metrics.

Evaluation Metrics. To evaluate forecasting performance, three commonly used regression metrics were computed for both the training and testing datasets after reversing the normalisation applied during preprocessing. The following metrics were used: RMSE (Root Mean

Squared Error), MAE (Mean Absolute Error), MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error). All evaluation metrics were computed using the scikit-learn library after denormalising both predicted and observed values using the same scaler applied during the preprocessing stage. Lower values of these metrics indicate higher forecasting accuracy.

Experimental Setup The models were trained for 100 epochs with a batch size of 32. For financial time series forecasting, the mean squared error (MSE) was used as the loss function, while the Adam optimiser was employed for parameter optimisation. The hyperparameters of the models varied depending on the time resolution of the dataset. The corresponding parameter settings are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Parameter settings for each model depending on the time tick. (Kumskov et al., 2025)

Tick	Units	Lookback
1m	16	30
1h	16	30
1d	16	1

LSTM The baseline LSTM model without fuzzification or parametric activation functions. Input dimension: $(lookback, 1)$. The architecture consists of: one $LSTM(units)$ layer, one $Dense(1)$ output layer.

Fuzzy Gauss An LSTM model with additional Gaussian fuzzification applied during data preprocessing. Local volatility (interpreted as the width of the Gaussian membership function) was calculated over the previous $window = 10$ observations. Input dimension: $(lookback, 2)$. The architecture consists of: one $LSTM(units)$ layer, two $Dense(1)$ layers.

PFS An LSTM model with fuzzification based on Probabilistic Fuzzy Sets (PFS). The number of intervals was fixed at $n = 14$ as suggested in the original method. Input dimension: $(lookback, n)$. The architecture consists of: one $LSTM(units)$ layer, one $Dense(n)$ layer.

Fuzzy Activation. An LSTM model with parametric activation functions. Three different configurations were considered:

1. Shared parametrization. All three sigmoid activation functions within the LSTM share the same parameters (+2 additional parameters).
2. Independent parametrization. Each of the three sigmoid activation functions has its own parameters (+6 additional parameters).
3. Full parametrization. All five activation functions in the LSTM are parameterised, with the tanh function replaced by a parametric sigmoid (+10 additional parameters).

Increasing the number of parameters leads to longer training times. Input dimension: $(lookback, 1)$. The architecture consists of: one $LSTM(units)$ layer, one $Dense(1)$ layer.

Fuzzy LSTM. The final proposed model combines fuzzification at the preprocessing stage with parametric activation functions inside the LSTM network. For the computational experiment, the configuration that demonstrated the best performance was selected: Fuzzy Gauss + Fuzzy Activation Variant 1 (i.e., Gaussian fuzzification combined with a single parametric sigmoid).

Software Implementation

All experiments were implemented in Python using the Google Colab environment. The following libraries were employed during the experiments: TensorFlow, NumPy, Pandas, Matplotlib, and Scikit-learn. The implementation of the proposed models, together with the scripts

used for the experiments, is publicly available at: github.com/MakhovaAnastasia/Paper_Fuzzy_LSTM

Results of the Computational Experiment

Minute Ticks For the minute-level time series, most of the proposed models demonstrated improved forecasting performance compared with the baseline LSTM model. In particular, the Fuzzy Gauss and Fuzzy LSTM architectures achieved the best results, with the Fuzzy LSTM model showing slightly higher overall accuracy. The forecasting performance improved by approximately 1.3 times compared with the standard LSTM model.

The PFS model demonstrated significantly worse performance. This behaviour can be explained by the large number of fuzzy variables generated at each time step, which increases model complexity and makes the model more sensitive to noise in the data. For this reason, the PFS model was excluded from further experiments with other time resolutions.

The results for the minute-level experiments are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of forecasting results for different models on minute-level ticks. The best results are highlighted in bold.

Model	Training			Testing		
	RMSE (\$)	MAE (\$)	MAPE (%)	RMSE (\$)	MAE (\$)	MAPE (%)
LSTM	54,9733	37,3272	0,0318]	58,3047	34,8402	0,0283
Fuzzy Gauss	44,8551	29,6470	0,0253	47,0182	26,8458	0,0218
PFS	140,6855	73,6051	0,0626	337,3356	275,960	0,2399
Fuzzy Activation 1	52,9521	35,8788	0,0306	57,5777	35,5182	0,0288
Fuzzy LSTM	44,8499	29,6360	0,0253	47,0379	26,8441	0,0218

Hourly Ticks For the hourly time series, all proposed models demonstrated better performance than the baseline LSTM model. Among them, the Fuzzy LSTM architecture achieved the best overall forecasting accuracy. The improvement in forecasting performance reached approximately 1.7 times compared with the standard LSTM model. The detailed results for hourly ticks are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4. Comparison of forecasting results for different models on hourly ticks. The best results are highlighted in bold.

Model	Training			Testing		
	RMSE (\$)	MAE (\$)	MAPE (%)	RMSE (\$)	MAE (\$)	MAPE (%)
LSTM	443,5242	314,5747	0,4826	569,2924	464,7323	0,4305
Fuzzy Gauss	390,0027	241,2795	0,3570	394,6866	266,7668	0,2518
Fuzzy Activation 1	410,3983	268,9249	0,4020	513,1758	400,4491	0,3708
Fuzzy LSTM	390,0251	241,2554	0,3571	393,1039	264,9332	0,2502

Daily Ticks. For the daily time series, the results showed a different behaviour. In this case, Gaussian fuzzification alone led to a decrease in forecasting accuracy. However, the use of parametric activation functions and the proposed Fuzzy LSTM model improved the forecasting performance. Overall, the proposed model increased forecasting accuracy by approximately 1.5 times compared with the baseline LSTM model. The detailed results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Comparison of forecasting results for different models on daily ticks. The best results are highlighted in bold.

Model	Training			Testing		
	RMSE (\$)	MAE (\$)	MAPE (%)	RMSE (\$)	MAE (\$)	MAPE (%)
LSTM		424,393		2564,027	1723,623	
	806,8518	1	14,9362	8	2	2,3658
Fuzzy Gauss		448,118		1665,308	1096,931	
	810,5163	0	21,7077	4	8	1,7346
Fuzzy Activation 1		393,587		3180,911	2204,956	
	836,4935	1	3,3283	1	9	2,9519
Fuzzy LSTM		423,186		1660,937	1092,267	
	804,5797	4	16,7181	6	0	1,7307

Training Time. Because the proposed models introduce additional parameters, the total training time increased compared with the baseline LSTM architecture. The corresponding training times for all models are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Training time of the models for different time intervals.

Model	Number of additional parameters	Training time (sec)		
		1m	1h	1d
LSTM	0	91.14	300.63	40.58
Fuzzy Gauss	$1 \cdot \text{lookback}$	90.14	314.33	42.83
PFS	$(m - 1) \cdot \text{lookback}$	222.60		
Fuzzy Activation 1	2	108.62	406.26	44.44
Fuzzy LSTM	$2 + 1 \cdot \text{lookback}$	111.65	393.45	46.51

Discussion and Experimental Conclusions

The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed fuzzy logic-based LSTM architecture improves forecasting performance across different temporal resolutions. Specifically, the forecasting accuracy increased by approximately 1.3 times for minute-level data, 1.7 times for hourly data, and 1.5 times for daily data compared with the baseline LSTM model. In addition, for daily observations the proposed approach reduced the MAPE value by a factor of 4.4, indicating a substantial improvement in relative forecasting accuracy.

The difference in forecasting accuracy across time resolutions can be explained by the scale and complexity of the data. At hourly and daily intervals, many external factors influencing future price movements are not directly captured by the input data. As a result, the model has access to less detailed temporal information, which leads to lower predictive accuracy. Consequently, forecasts based on minute-level data are generally more accurate than hourly forecasts, while hourly forecasts outperform daily predictions.

The training dynamics of the models were also analysed. In most experiments, the loss function quickly reached an asymptotic level after approximately 10–20 training epochs. Furthermore, the loss curves for the training and testing datasets exhibited similar behaviour, indicating stable convergence of the models and the absence of significant overfitting.

Conclusion

In this work, we developed a neural network architecture with memory enhanced by fuzzy logic for financial time series forecasting. Introducing fuzziness both at the data preprocessing

stage and within the neural network significantly improved forecasting accuracy compared with the baseline LSTM model: by approximately 1.3 times for minute-level data, 1.7 times for hourly data, and 1.5 times for daily data. The proposed approach integrates fuzzy logic directly into the learning process of the model and improves the interpretability of the network's decision-making mechanism.

The obtained results demonstrate the potential of combining fuzzy logic and deep learning techniques for modelling complex financial time series. Several directions for future research appear promising. In particular, further work may include:

- exploring alternative parametric activation functions, including parameterised versions of the tanh function;
- applying linguistic variables for the classification of market states and trend dynamics;
- incorporating reinforcement learning methods to design adaptive forecasting strategies and portfolio management approaches based on predicted values;
- extending the evaluation of the proposed model to a wider range of financial instruments and market conditions.

Another promising direction for future research is the decomposition of financial time series into low-frequency and high-frequency components. The low-frequency component typically represents the underlying market trend, while the high-frequency component corresponds to short-term fluctuations around this trend. In such a framework, fuzzification can be applied to the trend component using several shifted fuzzy sets (for example, left-shifted, centred, and right-shifted membership functions). This representation allows the model to capture deviations of the observed signal from the underlying trend. The high-frequency component, which oscillates around the trend, can therefore be interpreted and modelled through these fuzzy representations, enabling the model to detect short-term fluctuations and noise more effectively.

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